

CERTIFICATE

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

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RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALIDA

**DIGITAL GAME BASED LEARNING IN SECOND LANGUAGE: THE INFLUENCE OF VIDEOGAMES IN
LEARNING VOCABULARY**

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